

Newsletter

Building decentralised, distributed and local micro-grids for decarbonisation electrification challenge

HIGHLIGHTS OF THE LAST 6 MONTHS

The last six months have been an exciting period for the IDEAL4GREEN project. All 15 Doctoral Candidates (DCs) have now officially joined their host institutions, marking a major milestone in the project's trajectory. Since their onboarding, the DCs have hit the ground running, participating in an intensive Networking Week, meeting their supervisors and partners, and now actively progressing toward the first deliverables of the research work packages.

DOCTORAL CANDIDATES JOIN IDEAL4GREEN

We are thrilled to announce that all 15 Doctoral Candidates have successfully joined the IDEAL4GREEN network. Selected through a highly competitive process, with over 750 applications submitted, the DCs bring a rich diversity of backgrounds from across the globe, including profiles from Europe, Asia, Africa, and the Americas.

Each DC has been assigned to one of the eight beneficiary institutions and is supervised by a multidisciplinary team that spans academia and industry. Their research covers the full spectrum of the IDEAL4GREEN scientific

programme: from microgrid control and power electronics, to cybersecurity, energy market design, and policy frameworks. The project website www.ideal4green.eu has been updated to showcase the DC profiles and their individual research topics. We encourage the research community to follow the project's progress online and through our social media channels.

NETWORKING WEEK — JANUARY 26 TO FEBRUARY 2, 2026

The first IDEAL4GREEN Networking Week took place from January 26 to February 2, in Barcelona, bringing together all 15 DCs along with supervisors, partners, and invited experts for an intensive week of training, collaboration, and team-building. The event was a key milestone in the project's training programme, combining scientific sessions with soft- skills development and social activities.

The programme was carefully designed to maximise interaction and knowledge exchange. Highlights included:

- **Monday (Jan 26):** Icebreakers and team-building activities, followed by the Project Presentation by the Project Coordinator and Project Manager.
- **Tuesday (Jan 27):** DC Presentations and Institutional Presentations.
- **Wednesday (Jan 28):** Management Meeting with Partners, PhDs Soft Skills

Workshop, Steering Committee, and Research Activities sessions.

- **Thursday (Jan 29):** Expert Lectures by Adrià Junyent-Ferré (Microgrids) and Yolanda Castellón (IGrid), plus a visit to Wallbox headquarters and sessions with MDPI on Effective Scientific Writing.
- **Friday (Jan 30):** Expert Lectures by Titouan Delorme (Eroots) and Marc Pagès (TecnoCEA)
- **Monday (Feb 2)** Collaborative Research Planning sessions with FABLAB

The Networking Week fostered a strong sense of community among the DCs and provided a unique opportunity for them to interact with industry partners in an informal and collaborative setting. The event was hosted at the UPC (Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya).

Also you can check our YouTube video to know more about them and the project <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=fN1HfpJcQFY>

RESEARCH ACTIVITIES: PREPARING THE FIRST DELIVERABLES

Since completing the Networking Week, the DCs have been fully immersed in their individual research projects. Weekly group meetings have been established to monitor progress, exchange scientific insights, and support the preparation of the first deliverables across the main technical work packages.

WP2 – Technological Integration and Control

The DCs contributing to WP2 are focused on control architectures for microgrid integration, advanced power electronics, and distributed energy resource management. They are conducting literature reviews and defining their initial methodological frameworks, with the first deliverables due in the coming months. Regular weekly meetings are helping to coordinate efforts and identify synergies between individual research lines.

WP3 – Resilience and Reliability Enhancement

WP3 DCs are tackling the challenges of microgrid resilience, fault detection, islanding mechanisms, and cybersecurity. Weekly meetings have been instrumental in building a shared understanding of the state of the art and discussing methodological approaches to enhance the reliability of interconnected microgrid systems. Initial experimental setups and simulation environments are being defined.

WP4 – Planning, Policy, and Economic Feasibility

DCs in WP4 are exploring the socioeconomic and regulatory dimensions of microgrid deployment, including energy market design, regional inertia markets, and investment frameworks. Inspired in part by the Expert Lecture on Regional Inertia Markets delivered during the Networking Week by Luis Badesa, these DCs are mapping the current regulatory landscape and identifying key barriers and enablers for microgrid integration at scale.

MEET OUR DOCTORAL CANDIDATES

The IDEAL4GREEN network is proud to introduce the 15 Doctoral Candidates who are now driving forward the project's research agenda. Coming from diverse backgrounds and nationalities, they bring a wealth of perspectives to the challenges of microgrid integration and sustainable energy transition. Get to know them at www.ideal4green.eu/doctoral-candidates

DC1
Uxue Garciandia Irisarri

DC2
Yixing Du

DC3
Isabel Beatriz Jamett Rivera

DC4
Mark Frederick Puleston

DC5
Oran Murray

DC6
Javier Cano de Dios

DC7
Djobokou David Evi Josias

DC8
Amira Arif

DC9
Abdelkader Sallemine

DC10
Arsalan Rehmat

DC11
Aslan Eqbal

DC12
Enzo Alexander Cording

DC13
Emmanuel K Ngetich

DC14
Görkem Ünal

DC15
Mohamed Seralkhatm

LOOKING AHEAD

The coming months will be particularly productive for the network. The DCs will be submitting their first deliverables and continuing their research with increasing depth. Secondments to partner institutions are also being planned, which will provide the DCs with exposure to industrial research environments and strengthen the links between academic and non-academic partners.

Stay tuned for updates on the project's activities, publications, and upcoming events. For more information, visit www.ideal4green.eu or follow us on our social media channels.

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Ideal4Green

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MSCA Doctoral Networks 2023 IDEAL4GREEN project aimed at pioneering decentralized energy solutions to meet global decarbonization targets through innovative microgrid technologies.

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